

Angelo Leogrando^{1*}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

^oLUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Workers at Risk of Poverty in Europe

About 8% of European workers are at risk of poverty

The Eurostat measures the percentage of workers at risk of poverty in Europe. The indicator measures the percentage of people who are occupied and who have an income available lower than the risk threshold of poverty or lower than the value of 60% compared to the available national median income net of social transfers. An individual is considered as occupied if he works more than half of the year.

Ranking of European countries for the value of workers at risk of poverty in Europe in 2021. Romania is in the first place for the value of workers at risk of poverty in 2021 with an amount of 15.6%, followed by Luxembourg with an amount of 13.5% and Spain for a value of 12.7%. In the middle of the standings there are Lithuania, Hungary, and Austria with an amount of 7.5%. Belgium closes the ranking with an amount of 3.8%, followed by the Czech Republic with an amount of 3.5% and Finland with an amount of 2.8%.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of workers at risk of poverty between 2010 and 2021. Estonia is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of workers at risk of poverty with an amount of 53.85% or an amount equal to 3.5 units, followed by Hungary with an amount of 41.51% equal to an amount of 2.2 units and by Bulgaria with an amount of 29.87% equal to a value of, 23 units. In the middle of the standings there are the Netherlands with an amount equal to 1.96% equal to an amount of 0.2 units, followed by Austria with a variation of 0 and Sweden equal to an amount of -3.95% equal to an amount of -0.3 units. Croatia closes the ranking with an amount of -22.22% equal to an amount of -1.4 units, followed by Finland with an amount of -24.32% equal to an amount of 0.9 units and Lithuania with A value of -40.48% equal to an amount of -5.1 units. On average, the value of the percentage variation of workers at risk of poverty between 2010 and 2021 for the countries considered made nothing change.

Clusterization with the K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with the K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. In particular, the following Clusters are identified or:

- Cluster 1: Croatia, Denmark, Malta, Netherlands, Ireland, Slovenia, Belgium, Sweden, France, Czech Republic, Finland, Austria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Hungary, Latvia, Germany, Bulgaria, Lithuania, Estonia;
- Cluster 2: Spain, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, Romania, Poland, Portugal.

The analysis from the point of view of the median highlights the presence of an order of the Clusters as indicated below or: $C2 = 11.6 > C1 = 7.15$. From a geographical point of view, the dominant cluster or C2 is made up of southern Europe countries, while the countries of the central-north Europe have a lower value in terms of workers at risk of poverty.

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrando.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Network Analysis with the use of Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with the use of the Euclidean distance. A complex network structure and three simplified network structures is detected. Specifically, there is a complex network structure with the following connections:

- Cyprus has a connection with France for an amount of 0.52 units, and with Austria for an amount of 0.46 units;
- Austria has a connection with Cyprus for an amount of 0.46 units, with France for an amount of 0.39 units, with Sweden for an amount of 0.53 units and with Switzerland for an amount of 0, 43 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Switzerland for an amount of 0.52 units, with Austria for an amount of 0.53 units and with France for an amount of 0.45;
- France has a connection with Austria for an amount of 0.39 units, with Sweden for an amount of 0.45 units, and with Cyprus for an amount of 0.52 units;
- Switzerland has a connection with Austria for an amount of 0.43 units, with Sweden for an amount of 0.52 units.

There are also three structures with simplified networks or:

- Croatia and Slovenia have a connection for an amount of 0.52 units;
- Czech Republic and Finland have a connection for an amount of 0.38 units;
- Malta and Denmark have a connection for an amount of 0.42 units.

Conclusions. The percentage of workers at risk of poverty remained substantially unchanged in the period analyzed and equal to about 8%. This means that 8% of workers have insufficient income. These are the so -called working poors or poor workers, that is, of those people who also work poor. It should be considered that these workers are present above all in the countries of southern Europe where this phenomenon is even more serious if we consider the workers operating in the informal economy. In this regard, it is necessary to introduce salary economic policies that can integrate the income of workers at risk of poverty. It is very likely that in the future there will be various types of citizenship income that do not only concern unemployed people, as well as employed people who have insufficient income.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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Appendix

C2>C1

C1
C2

